

ENoLL Infoday

Accelerating Innovation Through Living Labs:

A Guide to ENoLL Certification and the use of Living Labs as Research Infrastructures

BRFFA, Athens, 19th January 2024 12.00 – 15.30

ENoLL (European Network of Living Labs) INFODAY, held on Friday, January 19, 2024, at BRFAA (Biomedical Research Foundation of the Academy of Athens), Athens, Greece, brought together key stakeholders in innovation, research, and technology. This significant gathering aimed to ignite collaboration, share knowledge, and explore emerging trends in the field of living labs (LLs) across Europe, with a particular focus on the Greek ecosystem.

The event was co-organized by the ENoLL, the Medical Physics & Digital Innovation Lab (AUTH), the Hellenic Institute of Transport (CERTH), and the Athena Research Center. This collaboration underscored their commitment to fostering ongoing discussions and collaborations among Living Labs.

Why Living Labs

The importance of living labs in fostering open innovation, collaborative research, and development was a central theme throughout the INFODAY. Representatives from ENoLL and prominent experts presented on various topics, including the benefits of LL certification, LLs as research infrastructures, and successful LL initiatives in Greece.

Presentations highlighted the power of living labs. These labs leverage open innovation and user-driven design to create a collaborative environment that transcends the boundaries of a single organization. The Quadruple Helix Model of Innovation, which includes citizens, research institutions, companies, and government agencies, is a cornerstone of this approach. This collaborative environment fosters trust and neutrality, allowing all participants to contribute openly to the innovation process.

Living Labs go beyond traditional technological advancements. They focus on implementing impactful changes across various aspects. This may involve developing entirely new or improved goods and services, streamlining processes for increased efficiency, or reshaping organizational methods for better business practices and workplaces. A core strength of Living Labs is user participation. End-users are actively involved throughout the innovation journey, ensuring that solutions address their specific needs. These Labs function as trusted ecosystems, empowering citizens to become active co-researchers. Their contributions provide valuable insights that are often missed in traditional research methods.

Living Labs also serve as vital research infrastructures for science and technology. Depending on the research and development stage, they can support scientific

advancements or technological breakthroughs. This modern research tool fosters collaboration and accelerates progress across various fields.

The benefits of Living Labs are wide-ranging. They provide a safe space to test and refine ideas, minimizing the risk of failure associated with traditional innovation processes. Living Labs also ensure that innovation happens in real-world settings, with solutions developed and tested under practical conditions. By connecting the research community and the marketplace, Living Labs bridge the gap between research and commercialization, facilitating the development of solutions with real-world applications. The iterative feedback loop inherent to Living Labs enables rapid prototyping and speeds up the innovation cycle. Finally, collaboration among stakeholders allows Living Labs to tackle intricate societal issues.

ENoLL Certification

ENoLL, the international non-profit association founded in 2006, is the global hub for certified Living Labs. It promotes the Living Labs concept, supports EU policies, enhances Living Labs' sustainability, and enables their implementation worldwide. Certification by ENoLL is crucial for maintaining quality and standards within the network and promoting a sustainable and authentic approach. It ensures that Living Labs uphold a consistent level of excellence in their operations and outcomes.

Certification by ENoLL offers several key benefits. It acts as a mark of quality assurance, demonstrating a Living Lab's commitment to excellence and instilling confidence in stakeholders. ENoLL certification also establishes a standardized framework for innovation worldwide, promoting interoperability and synergy between Living Labs. Additionally, certification serves as a criterion for ENoLL membership, ensuring a high-quality network of collaborators.

The Greek Living Labs Ecosystem

The Greek Living Labs ecosystem is a dynamic network of stakeholders from academia, industry, government, and civil society. Collaborating across diverse domains and regions, these stakeholders are committed to driving innovation. Some key characteristics of the Greek LL ecosystem include a diverse range of actors, fostering collaboration and knowledge exchange. Additionally, LLs in Greece span various sectors, promoting cross-sector collaboration and holistic problem-solving. Regional diversity is another strength, with LLs extending beyond urban centers to leverage regional assets and address local needs across Greece's diverse geography. Citizen-centric innovation is a priority for Greek LLs, empowering users to co-create solutions that are inclusive and socially relevant. Digital technologies also play a crucial role, enabling real-time monitoring, data-driven decision-making, and immersive user experiences. Finally, EU funding programs acknowledge the need for a supportive framework for LLs to thrive and innovate.

Conclusions

The ENoLL INFODAY at BRFAA, Athens, served as a platform for collaboration, learning, and innovation in the field of living labs. Through insightful discussions and engaging presentations, participants gained valuable perspectives and forged meaningful connections to drive positive change in their respective domains. The event underscored the critical role of living labs in fostering open innovation, enhancing societal impact, and shaping the future of research and development across Europe and beyond.

Overall, the INFODAY was a resounding success, reflecting the commitment of stakeholders to harness the power of collaborative ecosystems for collective progress and prosperity.

Key Highlights

- Inaugural address:** The event commenced with an inaugural address by **Evdokimos Konstantinidis**, *Chair of the European Network of Living Labs*, highlighting the significance of living labs in driving innovation and societal change. Dr. **Konstantinidis** emphasized the role of collaborative ecosystems in shaping the future of research and development.
- Opening remarks:** Next, **Georgia Ayfantopoulou**, *Coordinator of the ENoLL Zero Pollution Working Group; Deputy Director, Hellenic Institute of Transport; Founder, Thessaloniki Smart Mobility Living Lab (ThessM@LL)*, and **Panos Bamidis**, *Coordinator of the ENoLL Health & Wellbeing Working Group; Director, Lab of medical Physics and Digital Innovation; Founder, Thessaloniki Action for Health and Well-being Living Lab (ThessAHALL)* highlighted the progress made in the Greek ecosystem and welcomed the fostering of new synergies.
- Experts' presentations:** The INFODAY featured a series of presentations made by prominent experts and practitioners in the field. The topics were “**LLs in the EU landscape**” (**Evdokimos Konstantinidis**, *Chair of the European Network of Living Labs*), “**ENoLL goals and LL certification**” (**Martina Desole**, *Director of the European Network of Living Labs*), “**LL accelerating innovation and digitalization: the RAISE project**” (**Josep Maria Salanova**, *Coordinator of the ENoLL Mobility Working Group*), and “**Living Labs as Research Infrastructures: the VITALISE project**” (**Despoina Petsani**, *Coordinator of the ENoLL Health & Wellbeing Working Group*).
- Greek LLs Ecosystem & Demonstrations:** Experts and practitioners from the field shared their insight into current challenges, best practices, and future directions for leveraging living labs to address societal needs. Topics ranged from "Innovations in Healthcare Living Labs" to "Smart Cities and Sustainable Development." First, **Panos Bamidis** discussed “**The timeline of LLs in Greece and how the ecosystem evolved**”; he also presented the **ENoLL Certified Greek LL “Thessaloniki Action for Health and Well-being Living Lab” (ThessAHALL)**. Other certified Greek LLs followed. **Josep Maria Salanova** presented the “**Thessaloniki Smart Mobility LL**”; **Karamarkos Kon/nos**,

Senior Consultant on Urban & Regional Development, URBACT & EUI Lead Expert, JT & C4T, CINEA, New European Bauhaus, Regio-CEI-AMI Expert, showcased 2 LLs with the University of Western Macedonia (UoWM): “**Just Transition LL**” & “**Smart Living LL**” and emphasized the critical role of brain-drain in rural communities; **Apostolos Vontas**, Communities of Experience for Policy Design, LL member, presented the “**PolicyEX Living Lab**” and highlighted the need for policy making to facilitate planning, service design, ensure necessary funding, raise awareness, etc.; **Philippos Papadopoulos**, Director, Strategic Project Management Office, American Farm School, presented “**INOFA**” and acknowledged the importance of Greece being a member of the “**All-Ready**” network; **Michalis Katharakis**, Director, Mediterranean Agrofood Competence Center, presented “**MACCSOIL**” and welcomed any exposure actions that can foster new synergies; **Ebun Akinsete**, ATHENA RC, AE4RIA, presented “**Living Labs at the Sustainable Development Unit, ATHENA RC**”; **Eleni Toli**, AthenaRC, showcased “**Living Lab Modeler, A tool to leverage the activities and impact of your Living Lab**” and discussed LLM features & functionalities; **Pavlos Koulouris**, Ellinogermaniki Agogi, discussed “**Schools as Living Labs**” and the necessity of adaptations to the educational reality; **Paraskevi Chantzi**, Interbalkan Environment Center, presented “**Carbonica Excellence Hub: A Multi-Actor Platform for the Future Living Lab**” and the value of carbon farming.

Closing remarks:

Katerina Kouravelou, Director of the Hellenic Foundation for Research and Innovation (HFRI), commented on the Greek LLs dynamic and their potential for growth; she appreciated the different stages of maturity that are present in the Greek ecosystem, and welcomed the ENoLL Infoday Event as an opportunity to develop new synergies and push for further Research funding processes.

Panos Bamidis signaled that the Greek LLs are gathering momentum as co-creation and the Quadruple Helix Model of Innovation are increasingly trending. He also insisted on the need for certification protocols, as well as consulting services. Overall, he advocated for greater investment in the domain and urged for wider contributions and interactions that should be facilitated by recurrent events bringing together the Greek LLs.

